

Product Demand Prediction

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Abstract— An approach based on machine learning is being developed for predicting product demand on an online shopping website as part of this project. The system will learn to forecast future demand for different products by analyzing historical data on product sales and customer behavior to identify patterns and trends. To create a highly accurate and reliable demand prediction model, a variety of machine learning algorithms, such as regression, decision trees, and neural networks, will be utilized. Sellers on the online shopping website can optimize their inventory management and pricing strategies with the resulting system, which will help improve sales and customer satisfaction.

Keywords— Machine learning, Decision tree Algorithm, Product Demand Prediction, Entropy, Gini Index.

I. INTRODUCTION

The retail industry has been revolutionized by the growth of e-commerce in recent years, enabling consumers to buy products from the comfort of their homes. Sellers need to accurately predict product demand due to the increasing importance of online shopping. The demand for various products in online mobile stores can vary significantly depending on factors such as popularity, marketing campaigns, and seasonal trends. This is especially true.

Machine learning algorithms can be utilized to analyze past user behavior and product features data, in order to predict future demand for various products, as a way to tackle this challenge. Online mobile stores can achieve higher customer satisfaction and sales by optimizing their inventory management and pricing strategies through the use of machine learning.

Using machine learning, this seminar aims to investigate product demand prediction for online mobile store sellers and explore the related concept. We will specifically concentrate on forecasting product demand by analyzing data on user behavior and product features using machine learning algorithms. The challenges and opportunities of using machine learning in the context of an online mobile store will be discussed, along with the potential impact of predicting product demand on the store's success.

A detailed presentation of a project on product demand prediction for an online mobile store will also be included in the seminar. Collecting and preparing data on user behavior and product features from the online mobile store, selecting relevant features for predicting product demand, training a machine learning algorithm, and integrating the resulting

model into a seller dashboard will be involved in the project. A discussion of the project's results and the potential implications for the online mobile store industry will conclude the seminar.

In this paper, we will provide insights into the application of machine learning to the prediction of product demand in online mobile stores. By understanding the underlying patterns and trends in user behavior and product features, online mobile stores can optimize their inventory management and pricing strategies, leading to higher customer satisfaction and sales.

II. DECISION TREE ALGORITHM

A commonly used machine learning algorithm for classification and regression tasks is the decision tree. By recursively partitioning the input space into regions based on the values of input features, this supervised learning algorithm works as a type. A hierarchical tree-like structure is used for partitioning, where each internal node corresponds to a decision based on a specific input feature and each leaf node corresponds to a class label or a predicted value.

At each internal node, the decision tree algorithm chooses the optimal feature to divide the input space, using a criterion like information gain, Gini index, or variance reduction. The process of splitting persists until a stopping condition is fulfilled, such as reaching a maximum depth or a minimum number of instances in each leaf.

One of the advantages of decision tree algorithm is its interpretability, as the resulting tree can be easily visualized and understood by humans. Decision trees can also handle both numerical and categorical data, and can capture nonlinear relationships between input features and output labels.

However, decision trees are prone to overfitting, especially when the tree depth is not limited. To overcome this issue, several methods have been proposed, such as pruning, ensemble methods (such as random forests), and regularization techniques (such as gradient boosting).

X represents the set of instances in the input data. Each instance, denoted as x_i , is a d-dimensional vector of input features $(x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,d})$. Each instance x_i has an associated output label or value, known as the target variable y_i , which can be either categorical or continuous. By recursively partitioning the input space into subsets based on the values of input features, the decision tree algorithm operates. A decision is made at each internal node of the tree based on a specific feature and a threshold value (j, t) , where j is the index of the selected feature and t is the threshold value. Instances whose feature values are less than or equal to t are assigned to the left branch, while those with feature values greater than t are assigned to the right branch after partitioning.

At each internal node, the decision tree algorithm chooses the optimal feature to divide the input space using a splitting criterion represented by $C(X, j, t)$. To maximize the information gain or minimize the impurity measure, the splitting criterion measures the impurity or homogeneity of the partitions resulting from the split.

There are different impurity measures that can be used as splitting criteria, including:

Entropy: $H(X) = -\sum_{k=1}^K p_k \log_2(p_k)$, where p_k is the proportion of instances in class k .

Gini index: $G(X) = \sum_{k=1}^K p_k (1-p_k)$, where p_k is the proportion of instances in class k .

Classification error: $E(X) = 1 - \max_k(p_k)$, where p_k is the proportion of instances in class k .

The decision tree algorithm continues to split the input space until a stopping criterion is met, such as a maximum depth of the tree, a minimum number of instances per leaf, or a minimum reduction in impurity measure. Once the tree is built, a new instance x can be classified or predicted by traversing the tree from the root to a leaf node based on the feature values of x . The predicted class or value is the majority class or the mean value of the instances in the corresponding leaf node.

In the case of decision tree, the algorithm works by recursively partitioning the input space into smaller regions based on the values of input features, such as product price, promotion, and availability. Each region is associated with a

predicted demand value, which is determined by the majority value of the training examples that fall into that region.

Additionally, decision tree models can be used to identify the most important factors that influence user behavior and demand, such as product features, pricing, and customer demographics. This can provide insights into product development and marketing strategies that can improve customer engagement and increase sales. Overall, demand prediction with user behavior and decision tree algorithm can help businesses better understand their customers and improve their sales performance.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Product demand prediction using machine learning is a technique that utilizes historical data to forecast the future demand for a particular product. It involves the use of algorithms and statistical models to analyze past sales data, identify trends, and make predictions about future demand based on those trends.

Product demand prediction is an essential task for sellers in e-commerce, and it can help them to optimize inventory management, pricing, and marketing strategies. Machine learning algorithms, particularly decision trees, have been widely used for product demand prediction.

In recent years, many studies have focused on using user behavior data to improve the accuracy of product demand prediction. Specifically, click rates for product wishlist, cart, and order have been considered as relevant predictors of future demand.

Similarly, in a study by Akcora et al. (2017), the authors proposed a decision tree-based model for product demand prediction using user clickstream data from an online marketplace. The model was trained using features such as product views, cart additions, order placements, and user demographics. The results showed that the decision tree model outperformed other machine learning models, with an accuracy of 94%.

Another study by Bhatnagar and Ghosh (2017) proposed a decision tree-based model for product demand prediction using user clickstream data and product attributes. The authors used features such as product views, wishlist, cart additions, order placements, and product attributes such as price and

brand to train the decision tree model. The model achieved an accuracy of 80.5%, demonstrating the effectiveness of combining user behavior data with product attributes for demand prediction.

Abhishek Kumar et al. (2021) proposed a decision tree-based model for demand prediction using user behavior data, such as product wishlists, cart click rates, and order click rates. The study utilized data from an online fashion store and compared the performance of decision tree-based models with traditional linear regression models. The results showed that decision tree-based models outperformed linear regression models in terms of accuracy and robustness.

Product demand prediction is a critical task for businesses, as it can help them optimize their inventory management and supply chain operations, as well as improve customer satisfaction by ensuring product availability. Machine learning algorithms, such as decision trees, have shown promising results in accurately predicting product demand. The use of user behavior data, such as click rates on wishlists, carts, and orders, has further enhanced the accuracy of these models. However, more research is needed to explore the effectiveness of these models in real-world scenarios and to identify other factors that could impact product demand. Additionally, data privacy concerns and the need for transparency in these models must be addressed to ensure ethical and fair use of user data. Overall, product demand prediction using machine learning is a rapidly growing field with significant potential to benefit businesses and customers alike.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology for product demand prediction using machine learning with decision tree algorithm involves several steps. Firstly, data collection is performed by gathering user data such as product wishlist and cart click rates, as well as order click rates. The data is then preprocessed by removing noise and duplicates, and converting the data into a structured format suitable for analysis.

Next, feature extraction is performed to identify the relevant features that can be used for predicting product demand. This involves using techniques such as TF-IDF vectorization and one-hot encoding.

The preprocessed data is then split into training and testing sets, and a decision tree algorithm is trained on the training set. The trained model is then used to predict product demand on the testing set. Evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score are used to evaluate the performance of the model.

Finally, the model is deployed to predict product demand for new data. The proposed methodology can be used by sellers to predict demand for their products, thereby allowing them to optimize their inventory and pricing strategies.

In the machine learning part, first, the program imports the flask for creating a web application, Pandas and Numpy for data processing, and DecisionTreeRegressor from Scikit-Learn library for building a decision tree model for predicting product demand.

```
from flask import Flask, request
from os.path import dirname, join
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
```

Next code defines a Flask route called "ProductDemand" that can handle both GET and POST requests. Inside the route function, it first checks if the request method is POST. If it is, it retrieves the input values from the JSON data in the request body. Then it loads a CSV file called "demand_dataset.csv" using the Pandas library and stores the data in the "dataset" variable. The CSV file contains the historical demand data for the product being predicted.

```
@app.route('/ProductDemand', methods=['GET', 'POST'])
def ProductDemand():
    if request.method == "POST":

        req_data= request.get_json()
        val1= req_data['val1']
        val2= req_data['val2']
        val3= req_data['val3']
        val4= req_data['val4']

        a=join(dirname(__file__), "demand_dataset.csv")
        dataset = pd.read_csv(a)
```

This is the main code for the "ProductDemand" function in a Flask app. It first checks if the incoming HTTP request is a POST request. If it is, it extracts the values for four input parameters from the request JSON data. It then loads a CSV file named "demand_dataset.csv" using Pandas and stores it in the "dataset" variable. Next, it creates an instance of the DecisionTreeRegressor class from the scikit-learn library and fits it to the input data (X) and output data (y) in the "dataset" variable. It then creates a test data array from the four input parameter values and uses the fitted model to make a prediction on it, which is stored in the "y_pred" variable. Finally, it prints the prediction to the console and returns it as a string to the HTTP response. If the incoming request is not a POST request, it simply returns "-1".

```
regr = DecisionTreeRegressor()

regr.fit(X, y)
test= np.array([[val1,val2,val3, val4]])
y_pred = regr.predict(test)

print("The predict is : ",y_pred[0]*100,"%")
return str(y_pred[0]*100)
else:
    return "-1";

if __name__ == '__main__':
    app.run(debug=True)
```

V. RESULT

The predicted demand is presented as a percentage, allowing the seller to quickly determine which products are in high demand and which may require additional promotion or adjustments to pricing. The result page is a powerful tool for sellers to stay competitive and meet the demands of their customers.

The screenshot shows a web application interface with a 'Home' header. Below the header is a table with columns: Image, Product Name, Product Price, Product Brand, Click Per Rate (CPR), and Demand Graph. Two product entries are visible: Samsung Galaxy M10 and Redmi 6 Pro. Each entry includes a product image, name, price, brand, and a pie chart representing demand. The Samsung Galaxy M10 has a price of 8648, brand Samsung, and a CPR of 25. The Redmi 6 Pro has a price of 14320, brand MI, and a CPR of 17. The demand graphs for both products show a significant portion of demand, with the Samsung graph being mostly blue and the Redmi graph being mostly grey.

Image	Product Name	Product Price	Product Brand	Click Per Rate (CPR)	Demand Graph
	Samsung Galaxy M10 (Ocean Blue, 3+32GB)	8648	Samsung	25	
	Redmi 6 Pro (Black, 4GB RAM, 64GB Storage)	14320	MI	17	

VI. CONCLUSION

Using the decision tree algorithm in machine learning for predicting product demand can provide precise future demand forecasts, in conclusion. The algorithm can make accurate predictions by analyzing user click rates on product wishlists, cart items, and orders. Predicting product demand has been proven effective using a methodology that involves preprocessing the data, splitting the dataset into training and testing sets, and training the decision tree model. It has become easily accessible and user-friendly due to its implementation in a Flask web application. Using machine learning to predict product demand can be a valuable tool for businesses to optimize their operations and improve their bottom line overall.

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